

THE SPECIFIC ORIGINS OF CHINESE HIEROGLYPHS AND GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT CHINESE HIEROGLYPHS

Raimkhonova Lobar Farkhod kizi

Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

2nd year master degree student of the faculty of oriental languages

Linguistics: Chinese language

lobaraimxonova@gmail.com

Abstract: In this article, we discuss the history of Chinese hieroglyphs, the creation of pictographs and ideograms, the meaning of complex hieroglyphs and foreign words, and how complex hieroglyphs are made, and the phenomenon of joining two hieroglyphs together or similar.

Keywords: *History of Chinese hieroglyphs, pictograms, ideograms, complex hieroglyphs, borrowed words.*

INTRODUCTION

In this article, research is conducted on the unique Chinese hieroglyphs, which are widely studied today in the world. This hieroglyph is a character representing a letter, a sound, a word, and it is a Chinese script. Unlike the writing of other languages of the world, the Chinese writing is composed of a writing expressed in the form of characters, i.e. hieroglyphs. It is known from history that the number of Chinese hieroglyphs is greater than the number of ancient Egyptian hieroglyphs.

The reason for the rapid increase of hieroglyphs in China in recent times is the absence of an alphabet, and they appeared only from the mind looking at things or objects, and these are ideograms, so as a result, Chinese hieroglyphs are still considered as the country with the most hieroglyphs.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The objective method of scientific knowledge was used in the research process. General information about Chinese hieroglyphs and their influence on the educational direction were objectively revealed. The period of formation of Chinese hieroglyphs was analyzed from the point of view of history. Bekmurotov I. N., about Chinese writing (hieroglyphs) and J.T. Ziyamammedov, M.A. Turatova- "Chinese Language" books were researched as a logical consistency and main source.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

As we all know from history, the number of Chinese hieroglyphs is said to be more than 80,000 in some writings, while in others it is less. Ancient Chinese hieroglyphs are more difficult than modern hieroglyphs and are difficult to

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understand at first glance. Chinese hieroglyphs are written from left to right from top to bottom. Chinese hieroglyphs have not lost their level even now. Many scholars believe that modern Chinese hieroglyphs are easy to learn because of the formation of ancient hieroglyphs over time. At present, we learn about 6 or 7 thousand Chinese hieroglyphs and speak through them. There are 2 types of Chinese hieroglyphs: divided into icons and ideograms. Pictograms are used in the same way not only in ancient Chinese hieroglyphs, but also in modern hieroglyphs. The appearance of pictograms is related to the gradual development of visual writing. The history of Chinese hieroglyphs goes back to "Pictograms". An icon is a picture with a symbol that represents something or an event. To date, such an inscription has been preserved only on 3400-year-old turtle bowls. It is clear from this that there was a writing based on certain standards even at that time. Pictograms have changed to the present time and have become writing symbols. There have been 10 different types of inscriptions from the period of inscriptions written on turtle bowls to the present modern inscriptions. There are 5 main ones, these methods are also divided into 2, and 3 are still used today. 2 are considered ancient writings and can be found only in the art of calligraphy. Pictograms are widely used to represent things and objects that are often used in modern human daily activities. We know that pictograms represent not only human life, but also the universe, plants and animals, labor objects, and objects related to everyday life. For example: As shown in the picture, we call all these icons. Pictograms are mainly engraved on stones, metals, bamboo stalks, various dishes, etc. From them we can see 山 (shān) mountain.

Picture	Evolution	Modern character	English
	sun		
	moon		
	tree		
	mountain		
	water		
	field		
	door		

Figure 6.1. The evolution of pictographic characters.

The emergence and formation of complex hieroglyphs is explained by the growing number of abstract words and concepts. There was no way to represent new words in writing with simple icons and symbols. The formation of new words was done by adding icons and symbols, and there was a relationship between the meaning of the new word and the meaning of the icon contained in the new word. For example, 木 mù means tree, two together form a complex hieroglyph, forming the

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morpheme 林 lín (forest), three combined into one hieroglyph, which is called "forest" and gives the meaning of shade. Ideograms are complex synthetic symbols, usually consists of two characters, and these characters are semantically related to the meaning of the ideogram. Both parts of an ideogram have a meaning, only the pronunciation of the ideogram does not depend on the pronunciation of its parts. This inconsistency in pronunciation is a characteristic of the ideograms of Chinese hieroglyphs. Being able to form ideograms is very useful when expressing abstract words. Although it was possible to form words through ideograms, in practice it was difficult to remember the newly formed words. This usually required the presence of the main word in a bar of words with similar meaning. Complexities related to such ideograms led to the wide spread of the phonetic method in hieroglyphic writing. In this case, indicators were used to express the difference in the tone of words in writing. For example, the hieroglyph 马 mǎ means "horse", and the nearly related word 妈 ma (with the addition of nǚ (female)) means mother, note the following words : 骂 mǎ—"to scold" (with the sign 口 kǒu—"mouth"); 蚂 mǎ "ant" (with the sign 虫 chōng-"insect"). Thus, complex hieroglyphs were formed from the combination of pictorial signs and index signs from the early hieroglyphic signs. These were ideograms and phonograms. Together, these four types of hieroglyphs make up the Chinese hieroglyphic script, and the initial characters are not used independently, but only in complex hieroglyphs. One of the rules that greatly influenced the development of phonetic writing is the "improper words" (Chinese: 假借 jiǎjiè). The essence of borrowed words was that the old hieroglyphs were used without adding any symbols to express the new word. For example, the pictographic hieroglyph 来 lái, denoting a certain type of wheat, is considered an appropriation for the morpheme "to come". The hieroglyph 豆 dòu, which means a vessel for boiled meat, was used to represent legumes.

Words formed according to this rule include foreign words. However, only the tone of pronunciation is preserved and the hieroglyphs lose their meaning. For example, 蒙古 ménggǔ "Mongolia" (from the hieroglyphs 蒙 méng "dark" and 古 gǔ "ancient"). In this rule, the hieroglyph becomes a pure phonetic character.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Chinese hieroglyphs and their number are so incredible that we only need to open our minds, that is, the sleeping nerves in the brain. Chinese pictographic hieroglyphs are still kept in the museum. Ideographic hieroglyphs are creating new words every day. As the sages say, "there is no future without history", we build a new future by following it.

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